

VERSES FROM THE VAIDYANĀTHA PRAŚASTĪ AT ḌABHOI QUOTED
IN THE SŪKTIMUKTĀVALI OF JAHLAṆA, KEEPER OF ELE-
PHANTS OF KING KRṢṆA (1247-1260 A. D.) OF DEVAGIRI

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The Vaidyanātha Praśasti is a Sanskrit inscriptional poem by the poet Someśvara or Someśvaradeva, who flourished in Gujarāt in the 13th century A. D. ¹ It is a long inscription of 116 verses, and was intended to commemorate the reparation by king Viśaladeva (1243-1261 A. D.) of the temple of Vaidyanātha Mahādeva or Śiva in the form of divine physician, at Darbhāvātī or modern Dabhoi near Baroda. As is well-known, Viśaladeva was a king of the Vāghelā dynasty ruling at Anahilvāḍa Pāṭaṇ and was the son of king Vīradhavalā of Dholkā, under whom Vastupāla, the patron of Someśvara, was working as the minister. ² The Praśasti bears the date of 1311 V. S. (1255 A. D.).

This Praśasti is inscribed on two stone-slabs put into the niches on the inner side wall of the famous Hīrā Bhāgol (Hīrā gate) at Ḍabhoi. Unfortunately, both the slabs are very badly worn out. The writing on one slab is almost wholly obliterated, and no line on the other is now left entire, and consequently we can make out hardly one or two verses in their entirety.

The inscription was first published in 1892 in the *Epigraphia Indica* (Vol. 1, pp. 20 ff.) by Dr. Bühler from the photographs and rubbings supplied to him by Dr. Burgess, and the same is reproduced by Dr. Hirananda Sastri in *the Ruins of Ḍabhoi or Darbhāvātī in the Baroda State* (pp. 8-18).

It can be made out from the very scanty fragments of the Praśasti that the major portion of it extolls the warlike exploits of the kings of Gujarāt and of the Vāghelā chiefs and especially of Viśaladeva, and praises the buildings or renovations of temples by him. In the concluding portion of the poem (vv. 109 ff), Someśvara speaks of the officials and architects connected with the building of the Vaidyanātha temple, of himself, of the scribe and engraver of the Praśasti.

We can also see that some verses in Vaidyanātha Praśasti are also found in other poems by its author, Someśvara. As for example, the fragments of verse

¹ Journal of the Oriental Institute, Vol. 1, p. 10.

² Ibid.

6 are identical with his Kīrtikaumudī Mahākāvya II. 2 and verse 14 with the Kīrtikaumudī II. 99., and available portions of verse 25 agree with verse 27 of the Ābu Praśasti of Someśvara, commemorating the building of the Ābu temples by Tejapāla, the brother of Vastupāla, 1287 V.S. (1231 A.D.).

It is most remarkable that two verses from Vaidyanātha Praśasti are quoted in the Sūktimuktāvali, an anthology by Jahlaṇa.³ This must be within a very few years after the composition and publication of the Vaidyanātha Praśasti, because Jahlaṇa, the compiler of the Sūktimuktāvali, was almost a contemporary of Someśvara. It is also an eloquent testimony of the poetic fame that the Praśasti enjoyed within a short period after its composition.

Jahlaṇa was the keeper of elephants of the king Kṛṣṇa (1247-1260 A.D.) of Devagiri in the Deccan. Constant war-fare was going on between Devagiri and Gujarāt, but as a result of that strife, cultural contact got some impetus during the intervals of peace, and there must have been a good deal of give and take on both the sides.

The Sūktimuktāvali also quotes several Sanskrit poets of Gujarāt—some of them almost contemporary of the compiler—which supports the above statement. It quotes four verses of Vastupāla, the patron of Someśvara, and also gives the verses of others like the famous Hemacandra, Somaprabha,⁴ Śrīpāla,⁵ Vāgbhaṭa,⁶ Vijāyapāla,⁷ Prahlādana,⁸ Durlabharāja,⁹ Devabodhi or Devabodh,¹⁰

³ Published in the G.O.S., No. 82.

⁴ Author of the Prākṛit work Kumārapālapratibodha (published in the G. O. S., No. 14), Sindūraprakara, etc.

⁵ Blind poet-laureate of Sidhharāja Jayasimha (1094-1143 A.D.), king of Aṇahilvāḍa, author of the Praśasti of the Sahasraliṅga lake (lost), Praśasti of the fort of Vaḍnagar, etc.

⁶ Author of the Vagbhaṭālamkāra, a work on poetics.

⁷ Grandson of Śrīpāla (foot-note 5), author of a Sanskrit play, Draupadivayamvara.

⁸ Author of the Pārthaparākrama Vyāyoga (published in the G.O.S., No. 4), founder of Prahlādanapur or Pālanpur, a city in North Gujarāt.

⁹ Author of the Sāmudrikatilaka (1160 A.D.) and a minister of the king Kumārapāla.

¹⁰ The Prabhāvākacarita (ch. 21) says that Devabodha had come to Aṇahilvāḍa during the reign of Sidhharāja and had come in contact with the poet Śrīpāla. He is said to be an Ācārya of the Bhāgavata Sect.

Kumudacandra,¹¹ and Arasī Ṭhakkura or Arisimha.¹² Two verses are ascribed to the king Sidhharāja Jayasimha of Anahilvāḍa. The anthology quotes four verses of Someśvaradeva. In the history of Sanskrit Literature, we find more than one poets bearing the name Someśvara, but this Someśvaradeva appears to be none else than our Someśvara, looking to the acquaintance of the Sūktimuktāvali with the works of the Sanskrit poets from Gujarāt. The probability becomes stronger, when we know that our Someśvara prefers to call himself as Someśvaradeva, just as the compiler of the Sūktimuktāvali has done. This also shows that Sūktimuktāvali was compiled sometime after 1255 A.D., the date of the Vaidyanātha Praśasti, from which it quotes.

The anthologies seldom quote from inscriptions, and the fact that the Vaidyanātha Praśasti is quoted that way shows that it was considered a composition of high literary merit. Another inscription quoted in the Sūktimuktāvali is the Somanātha Praśasti, evidently an inscription from Saurāṣṭra (सन्ध्यातारडव० etc.) As the verse is not found in any of the extant inscriptions connected with the famous temple of Somanātha, it may belong to some earlier Praśasti of the same shrine, which was repaired more than once. Thus the Sūktimuktāvali has preserved very important literary data.

Two verses of the Vaidyanātha Praśasti quoted by Jahlaṇa are as follows :

सिन्दूरं सीमन्तात् स्मितं मुखाद्वैरिराजवन्तितानाम् ।

यस्य प्रतापयशसी हरतः स्म समानदृग्गुणासहने ॥ (P. 342)

यथेतत्क्षयवह्निधूमपटलं ज्वालाः किमन्तर्न त-

न्मेघानामियमुन्नतिर्यदि तदा किं नात्र विद्युच्छय ।

ध्वान्तं चेदिदमुद्गतं तदमुना प्रच्छायते किं रवि—

र्यद्यात्रोद्यतधूलिमिर्दिषिषदामेवं विकल्पाः कृताः ॥ (P. 343)

Evidently the first verse describes the valour and fame of Visaladeva, renovator of the Vaidyanātha temple, and the second one describes the march of his army. Owing to the utterly fragmentary state of the Praśasti at Dabhoi, these verses cannot be traced out there. And that is why these quotations are all the more valuable.

An identical case is that of the Praśasti of Sahasraliṅga lake, built by Sidhharāja at Pāṭaṇ, which was composed by Śrīpāla. Almost the whole

¹¹ Kumudacandra was an Ācārya of the Digambara Jaina Sect, and a contemporary of Sidhharāja. His dispute with the Śvetāmbara Ācārya Vādī Devasūri is the theme of the play Mudrīta-Kumudacandra Prakaraṇa by Yaśascandra.

¹² Author of the Sukṛtasamkīrtana Mahākāvya, a panegyric of the minister Vastupāla, who was his patron.

Praśasti is lost, only a small slab having been found, out of which a few broken lines can be made out.¹³ But some verses of this Praśasti are quoted by the Prabandhacintāmaṇi (1305 A.D.) of Merutuṅga and other works, and some stray portions of this important historical-cum-poetical work of Gujarāt are thus discovered. The same can be said also regarding the Vaidyanātha Praśasti, because it was also a historical document of considerable importance, composed by a famous poet of the times. If we get a transcript of it from some old manuscript, as in the case of Sukṛtakīrtikallolīnī of Udayaprabha and the Vastupāla-Tejpāla Praśasti of Jayasīmhasūri (both of which were originally in the form of inscriptions—the former one in the Indramanḍapa built by Vastupāla on the Mt. Śatruñjaya, and the latter one in a Jaina temple called Śakunikāvihāra at Broach, where the golden flag-staffs were installed by Tejpāla), it will be deemed a notable literary discovery.

¹³ These scanty fragments of the Praśasti of the lake Sahasraliṅga have been edited by the late Shri Rāmlāl C. Modī and presented in the form of a paper read before the Seventh All India Oriental Conference held at Baroda in 1933. The paper has been published in the proceedings and Transactions of the Conference.